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Schooling for College and Career Readiness: The Personalized Learning Reform Movement in the USA

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Abstract

This paper describes an educational reform project implementing personalized learning (PL) in a middle school. Personalization is the next stage of the choice movement and reinforces the logic of consumerism by bringing teachers and children into coproduction of curriculum and instruction. Yet classroom learning is individualized and infused with technology-enabled tools; and graduation competencies, course goals, and behavioral objectives are established one-on-one with the student. Additionally, project-based learning is featured for the development of soft workplace skills such as communication, problem solving, and teamwork deemed valuable in current employment settings. The state mandates students ages eight to twelve study occupational pathways aligned for college and career readiness. This pedagogical model features data analytics, reducing teaching and learning into newer forms of digital Taylorism.

Keywords

college and career readiness; digital education; personalized learning; school reform

1 Introduction

Personalization is derived from the neoliberal logic of new public management—that governmental agencies should be individualizing services for the purposes of enhancing customer satisfaction. Advocates believe personalization has the potential to transform citizens engaged in reshaping the services they desire; thus, becoming activists for reforming the public sector from the ground up. As showcased in North American schools PL features a digitized curriculum showing content mastery through customized and adaptive means. The Gates Foundation has funded PL demonstration grants throughout the country to increase the visibility of the reform model. Advocates charge that instructional technology will allow more students freedom to control their educational experiences. Online platforms vary from class to class and do not conform to traditional instruction as defined by the Carnegie unit, a uniform standard of contact hours earned for course credit. Digital education promoters contend that as a proxy for learning credit hours stifle educational innovation. Driving this reform movement are the domesticating narratives of human capital development.

2 Research methods

This paper is based upon a small-scale study of PL reform conducted at one middle school in Year Two of a districtwide restructuring to adopt personalized learning. The district was awarded a \$4 million dollar three-year grant funded by venture philanthropists at the Gates Foundation with additional support from the Dell Foundation and the Broad Foundation; one of a number of urban schools featuring technology-enhanced solutions “to dramatically increase the career readiness rates particularly among low-income students and students of

color” (Pane, Steiner, Baird, Hamilton, Pane, 2017, p. 3). The sixth to eighth graders in the middle school comprised a school population of 68% white, 21% African-American, and 7% Hispanic, and less than 1% Asian-American, among others. About 50% were on the free and reduced lunch program—a proxy for poverty. Three PL teachers, an administrator and a PL instructional coach were interviewed, instructional practices observed, and a number of artifacts and documents, including lessons plans and class handouts, course syllabi, school schedules, student learning pathways, and examples of student work were examined. The study explored how the design characteristics of personalized learning were incorporated into the state’s career and technical education pathway courses offered at the middle school. The researcher investigated:

- How teachers manage instruction;
- How instruction shifts in response to the incorporation of PL principles;
- What difficulties teachers face in their efforts to change instructional approaches.

3 The design model

Although there is not one common definition of personalized learning, the Gates-funded schools conformed to five design characteristics: (a) learner profiles, (b) personal learning paths, (c) competency-based progression, (d) flexible learning environments, and (e) a focus on college and career readiness. The middle school study adapted to the design characteristics just mentioned. First, the PL reform valorized digital media over print media. Students rotated into one of three 75-seat digital labs for about two hours daily (of the six-hour school day). This management scheme enabled scheduling smaller team-taught seminar-styled classes (under 20 students per class) in the core academics. Second, the PL reform featured competency-based instruction. Traditional teacher-centered whole group instruction was supplanted by a student-centered competency-based master plan. That is, lessons were tailored to students’ scores on pre- and post-tests, and levels of complexity were adjusted on an individualized learning plan. Yet the practice of personalizing instruction conflicted at times with the teachers’ view of customary whole group lecture format. Third, the school climate resonated with the spirit of corporate innovation. Each of the grade levels were assigned a semester or yearlong project in science or technology, STEM-related, requiring they work in teams to develop and complete the learning activity. And fourth, the administrators, teachers, and parents became boosters of the institutional makeover. Unlike direct instruction with lessons uniformly assigned to students, this model asked adolescents to take ownership of learning (within the confines of state-mandated standards) and act responsibly with self-regulating conduct that is uncharacteristic of teens prone to procrastination and laziness. Importantly it required school teachers dramatically change their instructional practices to accommodate digital education.

4 The critics

A number of critics deride neoliberal school reform as experimentation targeted to low-income communities considered lacking in college and career-ready skills. Some say the added costs deprive these neighborhoods from much needed local school district operating funds. Others are concerned about the lack of attention to academic comprehension by claiming reformers tout a skills-based curriculum that “excludes students from accessing the theoretical knowledge they need to participate in debates and controversies in society and in their occupational field of practice” (Wheelahan, 2015, p. 751). Those unable to judge

knowledge claims are marginalized in society. Schools ought to transmit what Young and Muller (2016) termed *powerful knowledge* leading to new ways of thinking about the world. Toward that end teacher-pupil relations should be characterized as hierarchical in that teachers hold specialized knowledge and certainly “will not be based, as some government policies imply, on learner choice, because in most cases, learners will lack the prior knowledge to make such choices” (Young & Muller, 2016, p.110). Fielding (2012) viewed multiple problems with this latest pedagogical reform as did Watkins (2012), who pondered how personalized learning could be deepened beyond its superficial description of individualizing instruction. And Preston (2017) strongly disparaged competency-based education and training because it reduces the activity of learning into a binary exercise, discounting the analog production of human movement and behavior “with no interest in the internal nature of our being” (p. 4).

5 Conclusion

By advancing the digitizing of public schools and classrooms the personalization movement contributes to the deskilling of teachers who become mere data collectors and analysts. “They no longer have to make pedagogical decisions, but rather manage the technology that will make instructional decisions for them,” claimed Roberts-Mahoney, Means, and Garrison (2016, p. 414). Namely learning analytics measure and collect data on students used by teachers (or their aides and para-professionals) to adjust personalized learning pathways, modify student activities, determine content mastery, record grades, and update learner profiles. Clearly multinational corporations like Pearson Education are advantaged by the worldwide market in personalized learning. Massive revenues are generated from the \$600 billion annual public education budget. U.S. Secretary of Education Betsy DeVos supports computer-based instruction at all levels of schooling leading to greater for-profit investments. According to Bulkley and Burch (2011), the education industry will “stimulate the demand and supply of education services and products in the marketplace by reducing financial risks for companies and non-for-profits and enhancing the perceived legitimacy of private engagement in public education as a reform strategy” (p. 244).

Due to the spate of federal mandates for high-stakes testing and pre-packaged scripted curriculum initiatives in low-income school districts countless teachers face a deskilling of professional work (Au, 2011). Yet newer processes of personalized learning via data analytics further erode teachers work. To be exact, data streams are generated by the digital assessment technology enabling staff members to create a profile of student scores on a continuum of competency-based skills. Then, an individualized education plan is prepared by the teacher *for each child* to assist with meeting his or her benchmarks. This activity contributes to what Roberts-Mahoney, Means, and Garrison (2016) maintained is an advanced form of digital Taylorism that

not only reframes education as a narrow private good oriented primarily toward efficiently preparing students for [the] twenty-first century global economy, it also serves to re-render complex characteristics of human beings into discrete “skills” that are transformed into data points subject to the authority of a computer algorithm outside the control of the individual student, the school, or the community (pp. 416-417).

College and career-ready discourses also enfold teachers into the maintenance of a disciplinary enterprise. As Sonu and Benson (2016) suggested, the child is “invited and coerced into certain kinds of activities” in compliant skills-based classrooms that fulfill the modern social imaginary of competitive advantage. “Here, we find that the child is both an

agent obliged to protect the prosperity of the nation, as well as the subject through which such interventions are inscribed” (p. 236).

As a final point digital education leads to job intensification and expansion because teaching duties are never ending. School administrators require teachers complete a number of bureaucratic tasks required for monitoring, documenting, and recording personalized learning. But consider the intensive labor involved in evaluating online activities. Selwyn (2016) noted how “evidence of each student’s ‘success’ might be based upon the sum of their tweets, blog posts, forum discussions and/or video uploads” (p. 63). Teaching online means reading and grading a number of assignments using interactive platforms. While students gain so-called clickable credentials by completing curricular requirements at their own pace, 24/7, teachers, too, are kept busy managing the course website. At any time of day or night they might be answering inquiries, posting announcements, monitoring student progress, uploading course material, and on and on. Even cleaning out one’s email inbox, Selwyn (2017) wrote, is “a necessary evil before commencing a day’s work” (p. 4, para. 4).

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Biographical note

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